
Research Article

New combinations in *Hoya* (Apocynaceae, Asclepiadoideae, Marsdenieae)

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Abstract: Six new combinations are proposed here under the genus *Hoya*. These nomenclatural changes are made to align with current taxonomic concepts of the genus.

Keywords: Endemic, *Eriostemma badaensis*, *Eriostemma davaoense*, *Eriostemma samarense*, *Eriostemma seidenschwarzii*, *Eriostemma smarense*, *Eriostemma suluense*, Indonesia, Philippines

Introduction

The genus *Hoya* R.Br. consists of about 573 species, including six species formerly described under *Eriostemma* (Schltr.) Kloppenb. & Gilding, and is distributed throughout tropical & subtropical Asia to the western Pacific (POWO, 2025). In Vietnam, the genus is represented by around 198 species, of which 174 are endemic (POWO, 2025). In Java, Indonesia, about 36 species occur, of which 15 are endemic (POWO, 2025). Recent phylogenetic studies have incorporated *Eriostemma* (\equiv *Hoya* sect. *Eriostemma* Schltr.) within the genus *Hoya*, which belongs to the family Apocynaceae, subfamily Asclepiadoideae, and tribe Marsdenieae (Rodda et al., 2020; Liede-Schumann et al., 2022). Based on the current circumscription and systematics of the genus, six new combinations are proposed here under *Hoya*.

New combinations

Hoya badaensis (Kloppenb. & T.Green) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma badaensis* Kloppenb. & T. Green, *Fraterna* 24(4): 16. 2011.

Distribution: Endemic to Java, Indonesia.

Hoya davaoense (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma davaoense* Kloppenb., *Hoya New* 2(3): 26. 2014.

Distribution: Endemic to Philippines.

Hoya samarensis (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma samarensis* Kloppenb., *Hoya New* 2(4): 4. 2014.

Distribution: Endemic to Philippines.

Hoya seidenschwarzii (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma seidenschwarzii* Kloppenb., *Hoya New* 2(3): 11. 2014.

Distribution: Endemic to Philippines.

Hoya smarensis (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma smarensis* Kloppenb., *Hoya New* 2(4): 4. 2014.

Distribution: Endemic to Philippines.

Hoya suluense (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma suluense* Kloppenb., *Hoya New* 2(3): 30. 2014.

Distribution: Endemic to Philippines.

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References

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